

The Unlikely Case of the Jewish Mercenary Nathan Leibowitz (1777-1810)

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In 1788, Emperor Joseph II ordered conscription to be expanded to include his Jewish subjects. This made the Habsburg Monarchy the first state in modern history to draft its Jewish population into the military.⁸ A further, albeit overlooked, consequence of this decision was the invalidation of a long-established ban on voluntary enlistment by Jews into the army. A middle category between conscripts and volunteers were substitutes, that is men raised privately to replace draftees called for military service. A noticeable minority of the Jewish drivers of the Imperial- Royal Military Transport Corps (*kaiserlich- königliche Militär-Fuhrwesens-Corps*) during the last Habsburg-Ottoman War (1788-91) were born in Poland rather than in the Habsburg lands.⁹ This suggests that local Jewish communities tried to spare at least some of their members by raising substitutes among foreign Jews. Foreign Jewish mercenaries who enlisted directly into the army out of their own free will were soon to follow. For instance, in 1794 Lazaro Isachi from Mondovì in Piedmont took service in the 44th Line Infantry Regiment ‘Belgiojoso’, which then stood on the Habsburg Italian military establishment.¹⁰ Between 1796 and 1798, the mercenary *Grün Loudon Freicorps* had in its ranks as many as 30 individual Jewish soldiers. A comparable number of Jews served in the Galician O’Donnell *Freicorps*, some of them joining as early as 1794.¹¹ To put these figures into perspective, while Jewish mercenaries probably numbered at most a few hundred men, from 1796 onwards the Habsburg army was drafting thousands of Jewish conscripts per year. Still, when Nathan Leibowitz enlisted voluntarily into the Habsburg army on 7 August 1798, the presence of Jewish professional soldiers in its ranks – both native volunteers and foreign mercenaries alike – was an established fact.

According to his personal records, Nathan was born in 1777 in Russia, albeit it is likely that before 1794 this was part of the recently partitioned Kingdom of Poland. He enlisted under the standard rate (*Werbgeld*) for foreign regimental recruits of 15 *Gulden*. The bounty (*Handgeld*), that is the cash bonus paid directly to the recruit, made only a fraction of that sum, as the enlistment money had also to cover his journey to his new unit.¹² For Nathan Leibowitz this

⁸ On the introduction and early days of Jewish conscription, see: Erwin Schmidl, *Habsburgs jüdische Soldaten: 1788–1918*, (Vienna: Böhlau, 2014), pp. 29–37; Michael Hochedlinger, *Thron & Gewehr: das Problem der Heeresergänzung und die “Militarisierung” der Habsburgermonarchie im Zeitalter des Aufgeklärten Absolutismus (1740–1790)*, Veröffentlichungen des Steiermärkischen Landesarchivs 45, (Graz: Styrian Provincial Archives, 2021), pp. 603–7. On the contextualisation of this phenomenon within the framework of Habsburg military reforms, see: Ilya Berkovich and Michael Wenzel, ‘[The Austrian Army](#)’, in: Alan Forrest (gen. ed.), *The Cambridge History of the Napoleonic Wars*, 3 Vols., (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 2022–23), Vol. 2, pp. 111–12.

⁹ For instance, the transfer papers of five Jewish supply and artillery drivers attached to the 28th Line Infantry Regiment ‘Wartensleben’ indicate that at least one of them was from Poland, see: Austrian State Archives [ÖStA], Military Archive [KA], *Musterlisten* [ML], 2438 IR 28 (1789): *Transferierungsliste* [TL] from 8 July, 23 August and 30 November 1789, as well as 14, 16 and 17 June 1790 – entries for Hersch Blützer, Wolfgang Galgenthal, Hanstel Salomonowitz, Jacob Schlosman and Hersch Knish.

¹⁰ ÖStA KA ML 3906 IR 44 (1795): Vacant (previously *Hauptman* i.e. Captain Renschberg’s) Company, Nr. 126 (Pavia 21/05/1795).

¹¹ See: Ilya Berkovich, ‘Jewish Mercenaries in Habsburg Service: Soldiers of the *Freicorps Grün Loudon (1790-1798)*’, *PaRDeS* 28 (2023) [forthcoming].

¹² On the type and size of the standard enlistment rates in the Habsburg army, see: Ilya Berkovich, ‘[Conscription in the Habsburg Monarchy](#)’, in: William D. Godsey and Petr Ma’á (eds.), *The Habsburg Monarchy as a Fiscal-*

was the 43rd Line Infantry Regiment ‘Thurn’ which was then in garrison in Friuli in north east Italy. It was six months before Nathan arrived at the regimental Reserve Division in *Laibach* (modern Ljubljana), the capital of the Duchy of Carniola. Roughly corresponding to modern Slovenia, Carniola was one of the smallest Habsburg Crown lands. In 1781, two of the duchy’s three administrative circles (*Kreise*) were allocated as the main conscription district of the 43rd Regiment. As nearly every other infantry regiment on the Monarchy’s German establishment, the 43rd also had an auxiliary conscription district in Galicia as well as a distinct recruitment region in the Holy Roman Empire.¹³ Galician conscripts and foreign mercenaries from the Reich were intended to spare as many native Carniolans possible from military service. Based in *Tarnopol* (Tarnopil, Ukraine) near the Russian border, the Galician conscription detachment of the 43rd Regiment was also tasked to raise as many foreign mercenaries as possible with the same aim. Presumably, this is how Nathan became enlisted.

Arriving in *Laibach* on 26 February 1799, Nathan spent the next two months there. After completing his training, Nathan left the city on 21 April in a convoy of 181 men to join the Regiment, which was already fighting the French in north Italy. 26 days later, Nathan arrived at his unit and was allocated to the Lieutenant Colonel’s Company. On August 15 1799, Nathan was wounded at the Battle of Novi, a hard fought victory against a French army under General Joubert. After recovering, he re-joined his company forty days later. Nathan continued to serve throughout the entire Italian campaign until the final Habsburg defeat in January 1801. Later that year, his Regiment was garrisoned in Dalmatia on the Adriatic coast. In August 1801, Nathan re-engaged in an open-ended contract. This meant he had committed himself to lifelong service. So far, there was nothing special in his story which can be reconstructed from the monthly manpower reports preserved in the Austrian State Archives. What makes Nathan’s case unique was his disciplinary record.

During his service, Nathan was arrested nine times. The first occasion was a two-day arrest in May 1800. In June 1803, he was arrested the second time. This time it was for 40 days. The third arrest, in autumn that year, was for more than six months. Three months following his release, in September 1804 he was arrested for the fourth time. The regimental muster shows that Nathan was left in the regimental headquarters in *Cattaro* (Kotor, Montenegro), some 300 kilometres away from his company’s new garrison in *Spalato* (Split, Croatia), suggesting military imprisonment rather than simple confinement to the guardhouse. A fifth arrest took place for forty days in autumn 1806 and a sixth for two weeks in January 1807. Upon release, Nathan was immediately transferred into another company. Transfer of deserters to other companies was common practice in that period, apparently to remove them from previous bad contacts. The same approach was taken with Nathan, whichever offence he was guilty of. This measure was clearly unsuccessful, as he was arrested again, four months later on 21 April 1807. Then on 12 June a court martial sentenced Nathan to hard labour. Two weeks later he was formally struck out of his Regiment, indicating that the trial proceedings were approved in the regional headquarters in Graz. However, this was not the end of it. The following month,

Military State: Contours and Perspectives 1648-1815, Proceedings of the British Academy 247, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022), pp. 308–9.

¹³ On the 43rd Regiment and its recruitment areas, see: Alfons von Wrede, *Geschichte der k. und k. Wehrmacht*, 5 Vols, (Vienna: Seidel, 1898-1905), [Vol. 2, p. 241](#); For a history of the Regiment, consult: Friedrich Dengler, *Kurzgefasste Geschichte des kaiserlichen Infanterie-Regiments Rupprecht Prinz von Bayern Nr. 43*, (Vienna: Stern, 1908).

Nathan was back. According to the manpower report, his sentence was amended, and, by order of the Aulic War Council in Vienna, Nathan was reinstated in service. A transfer to another company soon followed. This did not curb Nathan's disciplinary transgressions as there were two further arrests (for two weeks and ten days respectively) in April and October 1808.

The period in which Nathan lived saw a broader transformation of penal practices. Imprisonment was already used but was still not the first recourse for discipline. In the Habsburg military, the ultimate punishment was the death penalty, although from 1781 it was replaced with forced labour other than in the most egregious cases. Corporal punishment was far more widespread covering nearly every offense from desertion to drunkenness. Long term imprisonment made all the less sense, because soldiers under arrest still drew pay and provisions. Furthermore, repeated offenders were usually forced out of service somehow. Soldiers who deserted repeatedly were eventually sent to hard labour or executed. Crimes which fell under the civilian jurisprudence, such robbery, meant punishment in accordance with the scale of civilian courts. Repeated minor offenders under the military jurisdiction, such as drunkards and petty thieves, would tend to be ejected whenever the army was scaled down in peacetime. Nathan does not seem to fall within these categories. He was never implicated in desertion. Furthermore, during his service, the 43rd Regiment experienced disciplinary crises on several occasions. For instance, following the defeats in summer 1800 hundreds of soldiers deserted successfully in a space of a few months. There was another major desertion spree in spring 1806, when the Regiment was transferred out of Dalmatia back to Carniola. When many had deserted, Nathan stayed. Repeated thieving does not seem to have been the problem either, as this would have led to Nathan being kicked out of the unit. Besides, several imprisonment periods of weeks and months at a time, such as Nathan had, does not match the scale of that offence. Running the gauntlet usually resulted in immediate hospitalisation,¹⁴ whereas Nathan's only substantial periods in hospital were because of battlefield wounds. His numerous arrests did not seem to have been accompanied by serious corporal punishment. When finally sentenced to hard labour, he was in effect pardoned, suggesting involvement of the regimental top brass. There was something in his repeated offenses which appears to have made him respected, so what might that be?

On several occasions when Nathan was arrested, another man was arrested on the same day. In the first arrest, it was *Gefreyter* Anton Paul from the same company. Nathan's longest confinement started with his third arrest on 13 November 1803. On that day, Corporal Heinrich Heckert from the same garrison was imprisoned and then demoted. In spring 1807 when Nathan was eventually sentenced to hard labour, Corporal Johann Kozobinsky from the staff supernumeraries was arrested on the same day, spending two weeks under lock and key. Whilst this is only circumstantial evidence, it could suggest a pattern of behaviour by Nathan. Can we assume he was a serial brawler, who was not afraid of his superiors? According to the Articles of War in all European armies of the period, a physical assault on a superior – commissioned and non-commissioned officer alike – was defined as mutiny, which carried a mandatory capital punishment. In reality, as with duelling by officers, the military authorities were ambivalent when it came to fighting among lower ranks. Irrespective which form it took, from

¹⁴ In the first two months of 1819, all eight of the deserters from the Tyrolean *Kaiserjäger* Regiment, who were sentenced to run the gauntlet, were later admitted to hospital. Punishments ranged between four and six runs through 300 men, while recovery time took between four and 24 days. Calculations based on ÖStA KA ML *Tiroler Jägerregiment* [TKJR] (1819): *Standestabellen* [ST] for January and February.

spontaneous fistfights to a formal duel with seconds and witnesses, fighting between common soldiers was considered brawling and had to be punished. However, fights were often spurred by matters of honour – which was a universal military phenomenon which officers and soldiers shared. Harshly punishing someone who defended his honour could be seen as undermining the *raison d'être* of military culture.¹⁵ This helps to explain why duellists and brawlers were often treated leniently. Nathan's third arrest might be suggestive here. Beating a senior NCO could not be ignored. At the same time, a superior who could not maintain his authority to a degree that one of his subordinates assaulted him, could not keep his post. This might explain why Nathan was imprisoned for over six months, and why Corporal Heckert was stripped from his rank. Nathan's subsequent pardon from hard labour after his seventh arrest is also revealing. Since his case went all the way to Vienna, this means Nathan had patrons.

Nathan's eventual fate seems to suggest he was brave. In the War of 1809, his Regiment was part of the Austrian army which invaded the Napoleonic Kingdom of Italy. After recovering from the successful battle of Sacile (16 April 1809), the Austrians resumed their advance on 20 April.¹⁶ Next day, Nathan is recorded as hospitalised with thirty other soldiers, six from the same company, suggesting they were all wounded in a skirmish. This occurred long enough before a French counteroffensive in early May swept the Austrian out of Italy, capturing many of their field hospitals. Nathan was evacuated and in February 1810 his record stated he was 'sick in Hungary'. An overlooked consequence of the 1809 war was an outbreak of a typhus spread by the marching armies and ravaging the military hospitals and civilian communities alike.¹⁷ In March 1810, the 43rd Infantry Regiment was dissolved because the Duchy of Carniola was lost to the French. 964 soldiers – nearly all patients left behind in Hungarian hospitals – were kept on the record. In October 1810, 667 men whose fate could not be determined by that date, were removed from the regimental roll under the rubric 'fate unknown'. Among them was Nathan Leibowitz.

Appendix: Full Service Record of Nathan Leibowitz

Name: Nathan Leibowitz [Sometimes also referred to as Nosen/Nathan/Natal Leboviz, Natal Lepowitsch, Jacob Lewowiz, and Andre Lubiso]

Place of Birth: *Janislov*, Russia

Year of Birth: 1777

Personal status: Married

Profession: None

Height: 5.5.1 [171.37 cm]

07/08/1798 Enlisted in Galicia into the 43rd Line Infantry Regiment under a foreigner's rate of 15 *Gulden*. Allocated to Captain Höffern's Company. Since that that day, on the march to the Regiment with peacetime pay [ST Nov. 1798 & ML Jan. 1799]

¹⁵ Ilya Berkovich, *Motivation in War: The Experience of commons Soldiers in Old Regimen Europe*, (Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press, 2017), pp. 104–5, 120–22, 181–82.

¹⁶ John H. Gill, *1809 – Thunder on the Danube: Napoleon's defeat of the Habsburgs*, 3 Vols, (London: Frontline Books, 2008–10), Vol. 2, pp. 231–32.

¹⁷ Nebiha Guiga, 'Épidémies, routes d'évacuations et implications des sociétés civiles dans les guerres napoléoniennes (1805-1813)', *Revue Historique des Armées* 303 (2021), pp. 34–5.

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26/01/1799 Revision: IR 43 Captain Höffern's Company Nr. 145 [On his march here]
 26/02/1799 Arrives in Ljubljana and attached to the regimental Reserve Division with peacetime pay [ST Feb. 1799]
 21/04/1799 Marches out to the Regiment with wartime pay [ST April 1799]
 17/05/1799 Arrival in Captain Höffern's Company, and transfer into the Lieutenant Colonel's Company [ST May 1799]
 15/08/1799 Sick in army hospital [**The Battle of Novi**] [ST Aug. 1799]
 25/09/1799 Recovers and re-joins his Company
 28/05/1800 Arrested [ST May 1800] [**1st arrest, 2 days**]
 29/05/1800 Released [ST May 1800]
 17/08/1801 Re-engages on open ended service contract for a bounty of 20 *Gulden* [ST Aug. 1801]
 28/08/1802 Muster: IR 43 LtCol. Company Nr. 72
 18/06/1803 Arrested [ST July 1803] [**2nd arrest, 40 days**]
 28/07/1803 Released [ST Aug. 1803]
 02/11/1803 Muster: IR 43 LtCol. Comp. Nr. 63
 13/11/1803 Arrested [ST Dec. 1803] [**3rd arrest, 201 days**]
 31/05/1804 Released [ST June 1804]
 02/09/1804 Arrested [ST Sept. 1804] [**4th arrest, 128 days**]
 05/10/1804 Muster: IR 43 LtCol. Comp. Nr. 61 [Under arrest in *Cattaro*]
 07/01/1805 Released [ST Jan 1805]
 31/10/1805 Muster: IR 43 9th Fusilier Comp. Nr. 53 [*Sick in regimental hospital*]
 11/10/1806 Arrested [ST Oct. 1806] [**5th arrest, 40 days**]
 23/11/1806 Released [ST Nov. 1806]
 01/12/1806 Muster: IR 43 13th Fus. Comp. Nr. 71 [*Sick in regimental hospital*]
 01/01/1807 Arrested [ST Jan. 1807] [**6th Arrest; 16 days**]
 16/01/1807 Released and transferred to the 5th Fus. Company [ST Jan 1807 & ML 1807]
 21/04/1807 Arrested [ST April 1807] [**7th Arrest; 67 days**]
 12/06/1807 Court martialled and sentenced to hard labour [ST June 1807 & ML 1807]
 25/06/1807 Struck off the company's list as condemned to hard labour [ST June 1807]
 26/06/1807 As the sentence was amended during the transmission of the trial proceedings, readmitted into service and pay by order of the Aulic War Council (Vienna, 27 June 1807, Nr. 2531) [ST July 1807]
 15/07/1807 Transferred to the 9th Fus. Comp. [ST July 1807]
 18/04/1808 Arrested [ST April 1808] [**8th Arrest; 13 days**]
 30/04/1808 Released [ST May 1808]
 11/08/1808 Arrested [ST Aug 1808] [**9th Arrest; 12 days**]
 22/08/1808 Released [ST Aug 1808]
 06/09/1808 Revision: IR 43 9th Fus. Comp. Nr. 148
 21/04/1809 Sick in army Hospital [ST April 1809]
 25/02/1810 Disbandment: 9. Fus. Comp Nr. 119 [*Sick in Hungary*]
 31/10/1810 Whereabouts could not be traced. Removal from the regimental roll.

Archival records consulted

Austrian State Archives [ÖStA], Military Archive [KA]

ML 10.271 IR 43 (1799) – Haupt. Höffern Comp. Nr. 145 und Zuwachs (*Cividalle* 26/01/1799)

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- ML 10.272 IR 43 (1802) – ObristLt. Comp. Nr. 72 (*Cattaro* 28/08/1802)
ML 10.273 IR 43 (1803) – ObristLt. Comp. Nr. 63 (*Cattaro* 02/11/1803)
ML 10.274 IR 43 (1804) – ObristLt. Comp. Nr. 61 (*Theodo* 04/10/1804)
ML 10.275/6 IR 43 (1805) – 9. Fus. Comp. Nr. 53 (*Sebenico* 31/10/1805)
ML 10.277/8 IR 43 (1806) – 13. Fus. Comp. Nr. 71 (*Laibach* 01/12/1806)
ML 10.279 IR 43 (1808-10) – RL 9. Fus. Comp. Nr. 148 (*Laibach* 06/09/1808) & DL 9. Fus. Comp. (*Vordenberg* 25/10/1810)
ML 10.307 IR 43 (1799) – ST Feb. (29/04/1799), April (18/08/1799), May (22/09/1799), Aug. (06/03/1800), Sept. (21/07/1800)
ML 10.309 IR 43 (1800) – ST May. (??/??/180?)
ML 10.311 IR 43 (1801) – ST Aug. (13/07/1805)
ML 10.313 IR 43 (1803) – ST Juli (15/08/1803), Aug. (15/09/1803), Nov. (15/12/1803)
ML 10.314 IR 43 (1804) – ST Juni (15/07/1804) Sept. (15/10/1804)
ML 10.315 IR 43 (1805) – ST Jan. (15/02/1805)
ML 10.317 IR 43 (1806) – ST Okt. (17/11/1806) Nov. (15/12/1806)
ML 10.319 IR 43 (1807) – ST Jan. (15/02/1807), April (15/05/1807), Juni (15/07/1807), Juli (15/08/1807)
ML 10.321 IR 43 (1808) – ST April (14/05/1808), Mai (11/06/1808)
ML 10.323 IR 43 (1809) – ST April (11/10/1810) bis Dez. (23/01/1811)
ML 10.325 IR 43 (1810) – ST Jan. (01/03/1811) bis Okt. (22/03/1811)